

**ROLE OF PANCHAKARMA AND ŚAMANA CHIKITSA IN THE MANAGEMENT OF
EKAKUṢṬHA – A CASE REPORT****Dr. Geeta Patel^{1*}, Dr. Shreyas D. M.²**¹PG Scholar, Dept. of PG Studies in Panchakarma, Sri Kalabyraveswara Swamy Ayurvedic Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre. Bengaluru. Karnataka.²Assistant Professor, Dept. of PG Studies in Panchakarma, Sri kalabyraveswara Swamy Ayurvedic Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre. Bengaluru. Karnataka.**How to cite this Article:** Dr. Geeta Patel^{1*}, Dr. Shreyas D. M.². (2026). Role of Panchakarma and Śamana Chikitsa In The Management of Ekakuṣṭha - A Case Report. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 12(7), 290-294. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

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ABSTRACT

Kushta is the broad spectrum word used in ayurveda to describe all the skin diseases under one heading which is mainly classified into *mahakushta* and *kshudra kushta*. It is of prime importance due to chronic and severity which involves larger extent of the body. In contemporary to Plaque Psoriasis, In the present study we have reported 50 years old female patient came with complaints of severe dryness of the skin, white scaly powdery discharge with severe itching and burning sensation for three years, with history of Diabetes Mellitus. The treatment protocol adopted here are *Antaha Parimarjana chikitsa (shodhana)* and *Bahir Parimarjana chikitsa (sarvanaga abyanaga and sarvanaga parisheka)* and *shamanoushadhis*. After treatment, patient got satisfactory results and complaints are reduced by 60-70%.

INTRODUCTION

In Ayurveda, almost all the skin diseases are described under *Kushta Rogadhikara*. *Kushta* is considered to be *Ashtamhagada Roga*.^[1] and *Aupasargika Roga*.^[2] As per Acharya Charaka, the vitiation of *Tridosha* along with *Twak, Rakta, Mamsa, and Lasika* have major role in the pathogenesis of *Kushta*.^[3] *Ekakushta* is one among the 11 types of *Kshudra kushta* which is characterized by, *Aswedana* (absence of sweating), *Mahavastu* (covers entire body) and *Matsyashakalopma* (resembles the scales of fish).^[4] Acharya Bhavaprakash^[5] describes that, the lesions of *ekakushta* are in *chakrakara* (circular in shape), *Abhrakapatrasama* (silver colored mica sheets). It primarily manifests due to imbalance in the *Vata-Kapha Dosh* and *Rakta* as *Pradhana Dushya*.

Psoriasis is an inflammatory, hyperproliferative skin condition that is persistent and immune-mediated.^[5] In the world, prevalence of psoriasis is approximately 2-3%. In India, prevalence of Psoriasis is ranges from 0.44%-2.8%.^[6] Psoriasis affects number of body parts, including the scalp, face, chest, trunk, limbs, palms soles. Psoriasis has a significant negative influence on patient's psychological and social wellbeing due to its chronic

nature, recurrent pattern and visibility. Clinically, *Ekakushta* is characterized by *Aswedana* (lack of sweating), *Mahavastu* (large and extensive lesions) and *Matsyashakalopma* (appearance resembling fish scales). These clinical features show a close resemblance to the manifestations of psoriasis, therefore, therapeutic principles adopted for *Eka kushta* can be considered applicable in such conditions. In Ayurveda, *Ekakushta* is managed through multimodal approach incorporating both *Antah Parimarjana Chikitsa* and *Bahir Parimarjana chikitsa*. Considering the chronic and relapsing-remitting nature of the disease, characterized by frequent exacerbation and periods of remission, a comprehensive treatment approach is essential. Therefore, the administration of *Shodhana Chikitsa* as the primary line of management to eliminate vitiated *Doshas* and correct underlying pathophysiology, followed by *Shamana Aushadhis* to stabilize the disease process, prolong remission, and minimize recurrence.

CASE REPORT

A 50 year female patient visited Panchakarma OPD of SKAMCH and RC on Date 22/12/2025 with following details:

Age/Sex:50yr/female
 OPD NO:M40184
 DOA:22/12/25
 DOD:06/01/26
 Address: Chamrajpet, Bangalore

Chief Complaints

- Scaly lesions all over the body, severe itching and burning sensation for past 3 years
- Peeling of skin and dandruff since 6 months
- Reddish and blackish discoloration of skin

Associated Complaints

- Disturbed sleep since 1 year
- Loss of appetite since 1 month

H/O Present Illness

A 50 Year old female presented with complaints of scaly skin lesions associated with itching and burning sensation since 3 years. The condition started as a small erythematous patch over the neck and gradually spread to the trunk and extremities. Patient was treated conservatively at Allopathic Hospital. But didn't got any satisfactory results. Later she got admitted in SKAMCH and RC for further management.

Past History

- K/C/O of Diabetes mellitus type 2

Personal History

- Diet -Mixed
- Appetite-Poor
- Bowel -Hard stools (on and off constipation)
- Sleep-Disturbed because of itching
- Micturition-5-6 times in a day, 2 to 3 times in a night

Family history

Patient younger brother is Diabetic

Vital examination

- Pulse rate 78bpm
- Respiratory rate 18cpm
- Heart rate 72bpm
- Blood pressure 130/80 mmhg

Nidana panchaka

Nidana -Virudha Aahara and Vihara Sevana, Dadhi Sevana, Ati katu and Amla Rasa Sevana

Purvarupa -Kandu, Daha

Anupashaya-Exposure to too cold and hot weather

Samprapti

Nidana sevana

Tridosha Prakopa

Dosha-Dushya samurchana (saphaka Dravya sangraha – Tridosha, Twacha, Rakta, Mamsa and Lasika)

Khavaigunyata in Twacha

Lakshanas like Aswedana, Mahavastu and Matsyahakalopama appeared in Twacha of Ekakushta

Samprapti Ghatakas

Dosha-Pitta Pradhana Tridosha

Dushya-Rasa, Rakta, Mamsa, Mamsavaha, Ambuvaha

Srotodushti-Sangha

Agni-Jataragni, Dhatwagni and Bhutagni

Ama-Jataragnijanya ama, Dhatwagnijanya ama and Bhutagnijanya ama

Udbhavasthana- Amashaya

Sancharasthana-Rasayani

Vyakta sthana-Sarvashareera

Rogamarga-Bahya Rogamarga

Sadyaasdhyaata-Kasta Sadya

Tabel 01: Ashtasthana pariksha.

Nadi	78bpm
Mala	Vibandha
Mutra	Prakrita
Jihwa	Ishat Liptata
Shabda	Prakrita
Sparsha	Anushana Sheetha
Druk	Prakrita
Akriti	Madhyama

Table 02: Dashavidha Pariksha.

Prakruti	Vata-Pitta
Vikriti	Tridosha+Rakta
Sara	Madhyama
Samhana	Pravara
Pramana	Madhyama
Satwa	Madhyama
Satmya	Shadrasa
Aharashakti	Madhyama
Vyayamashakti	Pravara
Vaya	Madhyama

Systemic examination

Respiratory System: Normal Vesicular Breath Sound

Cardiovascular system: S1 S2 heard. No added sound heard.

Central Nervous System: Patient is conscious and oriented to time, place and person

Gastro-Intestinal System: Soft and non tender

Integumentary system examination

Site-Scalp, Chest, Abdomen, Extensor part of upper and lower limbs and Trunk.

Shape-Irregular scaly reddish patch

Size -Multiple, No specific size

Color-Pink white

Uniformity-Generalized Plaques

Boundary-Not well demarcated

Lesions-Plaques

Special Test in Plaque Psoriasis

- a) Candle grease sign -Positive (Presence of dry white scaly discharge)
- b) Auspitz sign- Positive (presence of pinpoint-like bleeding foci that appear when plaques are scraped deeper)

MATERIAL AND METHODS**Table 03: Shodhana (from 22/12/25 to 1/6/26).**

Date	Procedure	Aoushadha	Days
22/12/25	<i>Sarvanga parisheka</i>	<i>guduchi(50gms)+Triphala churna(50gms)</i>	09days
22/12/25	<i>Sarvanga Abhyanga</i>	<i>Ayappa kera taila</i>	09days
22/12/25	<i>Shirodhara</i>	<i>Guduchi churna(50gms)Triphala churna(50gms)</i>	09days
31/12/25	<i>Arohana snehapana matra</i> Day 01-30ml Day 02-70ml Day 03-90ml	<i>Tiktaka ghrita</i>	03 days
3/1/26	<i>Sarvanga Abhyanga f/b</i> <i>Sarvanga parisheka</i>	<i>Ayyapala kera taila</i> <i>Triphala +Godanti churna</i>	03 days
6/1/26	<i>Virechana</i>	<i>Trivrut Lehya (50gms)</i>	1 day
7/1/26	<i>Samsarjana karma</i>	<i>Peyadi</i>	3 days

Follow Up After 15 days**Table 04: Shamanoushadhis.**

<i>Guggulutikta Kashaya</i>	15ml-0-15ml with 30 ml warm water
<i>Triphala churna</i>	0-0-1tsp with warm water
<i>Ayyapala kera taila</i>	External application
<i>MadhuSnuhiRasayana</i>	1tsp-0-0(Before food)

Assessment Criteria

Subjective Criteria

Gradation Scales^[8]**Table 05: Aswedanam.**

Grade	Score
Normal	0
Improvement	1
Present in few lesions	2
Present in all lesions	3
<i>Aswedanam</i> in lesions and uninvolved skin	4

Table 06: Kandu.

Grade	Score
No itching	0
Occasional itching	1
Frequent but tolerate itching	2
Very severe itching due to which disturb sleep	3

Table 07: Rukshata.

Grade	Score
Normal	0
Slightly dry skin	1
Excessively dry skin	2
Linchenified	3
Bleeding through the skin	4

Objective Criteria**Table 08: Mahavastu.**

Grade	Score
No lesions on <i>mahasthanam</i>	0
Lesion on partial parts of Hand, Leg, Neck, Scalp	2
Lesion on whole body	3

Table 09: Scaling.

Grade	Score
No Scaling	0
Mild Scaling by rubbing/by itching	1
Moderate Scaling by rubbing/by itching	2
Severe Scaling by rubbing/by itching	3

Table 10: Candle grease sign, Auspitz sign.

Grade	Score
Absent	0
Present	1

OBSERVATIONS**Table 11: Following observation were found before and after the intervention.**

Clinical feature	Before treatment	After treatment
<i>Aswedanam</i>	3	1
<i>Kandu</i>	3	2
<i>Rukshata</i>	2	1
<i>Mahavastu</i>	4	2
Scaling	3	0
Candle grease sign	1	0
Auspitz sign	1	0

RESULT

Significant improvement was observed in the subjective parameters of the patient.

DISCUSSION

Psoriasis is an inflammatory, hyperproliferative skin condition that is persistent and immune-mediated. Clinically, *Ekakushtha* is characterized by *Aswedana*(lack

of sweating), *Mahavastu* (large and lesions) and *Matsayshakalopma* (appearance resembling fish scales). These clinical features show a close resemblance to the manifestations of psoriasis, therefore, therapeutic principles adopted for *Ekakushtha* can be considered applicable in such conditions. The line of management primarily includes repeated administration of *Shodhana* (purification) and *Shamana* (palliative therapy), which is the standard approach for all *kushtas*. In this case *Sarvanga abhyanga*, *Sarvanga parisheka*, *Shirodhara* followed by *Virechana karma* was planned.

The aforementioned information led to the adaptation of *shodhana* i.e., *virechana* which helps in the elimination of *doshas* from the body and stops recurrence.

Probable mode of action of intervention

Sarvanga abhyanga: *sarvanga abhyanga* with *Ayyappalakeratailam*. It contains *Swetakutaja* (*wrightia tinctoria*) and *Nimba* (neem) which reduces itching, scaling, and inflammation.

Sarvanga Parisheka with *Triphala churna* (50gm) + *Guduchi churna* (50gm)

Shirodhara with *Triphala churna* + *Guduchichurna*

Virechana karma

Purvakarma: *Tiktakghrita* was selected for *snehapana*. It contains *patola*, *nimba*, *katuki*, *darvi*, *duralabha*, *parpata*, *trayamana*, *trayanti*, *musta*, *bhunimba*, *kalinga*, *kana*, *sarpi*.

This *ghrita* possess *tikta pradhana rasa* and acts as *pitta shamaka*. Mainly indicated in *kushta*. It helps to bring *dosha* from *shaka* to *koshta* where dis vitiated *doshas* can be removed through *virechana karma*.

During vishrama kala: *Ayyapala keratailam* was selected for *Sarvanga abhyanga* as it is mainly indicated in *kandu* and *Sarvanga parisheka* with *triphala churna* and *guduchi churna* was done.

Pradhana karma: *Truvrit lehya* is selected as *virechana Dravya*. As this *lehya* contains *trivrut kalka* and *trivurt kashya* which acts as *sukha virechaka*.

Virechana is mainly indicated in *Rakta Pitta dushti*. As *virechana dravya* contains *vyavayi*, *vikasi*, *Sukshma gunas* responsible for quick absorption of medicines. Mainly due to *Prabhava*, *Prithvi* and *Jala* constitution and presence of *Sara guna*, *virechana* occurs, thus helps in the evacuation of vitiated *doshas* from the body. Thus helps in pacifying *kushta*.

Pashchat karma: *Peyadi samsarjana karma* was advised, as it helps to kindle the *agni*.

Shamanoushadhis

a) Gugglu tikitka Kashaya: It is indicated in *ekakushtha* due its *Tikta rasa* dominant drugs which perform *Rakta-shodhana*, *Kledashoshana* and *kapha-pitta shamana*.

Gugglu adds *lekhana*, *Shothahara* and *srotoshodhana* actions, thereby reducing scaling, inflammation and thickened lesions seen in *ekakushtha*. Modern studies show that *Commiphora mukul* exhibits anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and immunomodulatory properties due to bioactive constituents such as *guggulsterones*, which help regulate inflammatory mediators associated with psoriasis.

b) Triphalachurna: It is composed of *Haritaki* (*Terminalia chebula*), *Bibhitaki* (*Terminalia bellirica*), *Amalaki* (*Phyllanthus emblica*). In *Charaka Samhita* and *ashtanga Hridaya*, *Triphala* is widely described for its *Rasayana kustaghana* and mild *Anuloma* properties. The pathogenesis of *ekakushtha* involves derangement of *vata* and *kapha dosha doshas* along with *Rakta dushti* and impaired *agni* leads to *ama* formation. *Triphala* helps in correcting *agnimandya* through its *Deepana* and *Pachana* properties and facilitates the elimination of vitiated *doshas* through its mild *Anuloma* action. By improving digestion and clearing *ama*, it helps to prevent further pathological progression of *kushta*. Furthermore, *Triphala* acts as a *rasayana* that promotes tissue rejuvenation and improves skin integrity. From modern pharmacological perspective, *Triphala* possesses significant antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial and immunomodulatory activities. These properties help reduce oxidative stress, inflammatory processes involved in psoriasis like conditions.

c) Ayyapala kera taila: Its mentioned in *sahasrayoga taila prakarana*. The presence of *Wrightia tinctoria* (*Swetakutaja*) is recognized for its *kushtaghana*, *kandughna* and *vata-kapha shamaka* properties, beneficial in *ekakushtha* characterized by dryness, scaling, and thickened plaques. The coconut oil base acts as *Snigdha* medium that nourishes the skin, alleviates dryness and restores the skin. The formulation helps restore the normal structure and function of the skin by reducing excessive scaling and irritation. Modern studies demonstrated that *Wrightia tinctoria* possesses anti-psoriatic, anti-inflammatory and anti microbial activities, which help regulate abnormal keratinocyte proliferation and reduce inflammation in psoriasis like conditions.

d) Madhusnuhi rasayana: *Madhusnuhi Rasayana*, described in *sahasrayoga (Leha Prakarana)*, is indicated in *Kushtha* and chronic inflammatory disorders. It possesses *Tikta-kashaya rasa* with *rasayana* and *rakashodhaka* properties, thereby correcting *rakta dushti* and *kleda* in skin diseases like *Ekakushtha*. Pharmacologically, immunomodulatory and antioxidant activities, which help in reducing keratinocyte proliferation, inflammation and oxidative stress.

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